

Kinetics of Reaction between Hydroxylamine and Iodine

K. Chakravarti and Kalyan K. Sengupta

Hydroxylamine can be oxidised by various oxidants like Fe(III)¹⁻², Ce(IV)³, K₃Fe(CN)₆⁴, and bromate⁵. The reaction between hydroxylamine and iodine does not appear to have been studied so far from the kinetics standpoint. Some of the results of such a reaction have been recorded here.

The materials used were of the highest possible purity (E. Merck). Iodine (0.1*N*) with known excess of KI, thiosulphate (0.025*N*), and 1% starch solutions were prepared. The solution of hydroxylamine was estimated by the method of oxidation with bromate. An excess of bromate was added and back-titrated volumetrically⁶. Iodine solution was estimated by a standard thiosulphate solution. pH-adjustments were made by varying the amount of H₂SO₄ (dil.) in the mixture. Measurements of pH were carried out in a photo-volt pH-meter.

Solutions of hydroxylamine and iodine were kept separately in a constant temperature bath until these attained the desired temperatures and then mixed together rapidly. Aliquot parts were withdrawn at suitable intervals of time and titrated by a standard thiosulphate solution. The reaction was found to be of first order with respect to both the reagents. The reaction was followed up to 60% conversion and the first order rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the linear plots (always including 6-8 experimental points).

TABLE I
Oxidation of hydroxylamine by iodine solution.

NH ₂ OH.	Iodine.	Iodide.	pH.	Temp.	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹).
0.0208 <i>N</i>	0.02080 <i>N</i>	0.0833 <i>N</i>	1.70	30°	9.212
"	"	"	1.60	"	5.374
"	"	"	1.54	"	2.303
"	"	"	1.48	"	1.535
"	"	"	1.37	"	1.259
"	"	"	0.92	"	0.192
0.0166	0.01660	0.0832	1.74	"	5.374
"	"	0.0900	"	"	4.606
"	"	0.1166	"	"	2.685
"	"	0.1332	"	"	0.981
"	0.00820	0.0583	"	32°	3.840
0.0145	0.00725	0.6666	"	"	3.070
0.0166	0.00827	0.0333	"	"	6.909
"	"	"	"	28°	5.373
"	"	"	"	16°	3.840
"	"	"	"	6°	2.303

1. Meyeringh, *Ber.*, 1942, 75, 1877.

2. Ebler and Schott, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1908, 78, 320.

3. Benrath and Ruland, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 114, 267.

4. Sant, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1955, 145, 257.

5. Wagner, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 120, 261.

6. Kolthoff and Belcher, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. III, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, p. 552, 1957.

Effect of Iodide-ion Concentration.—The reaction was studied at different iodide-ion concentrations. The rate constant decreased with increase of iodide-ion concentration. The results are recorded in Table I.

Effect of Iodine Concentration on the Reaction Velocity.—Some of the experiments were also performed at different concentration of the iodine solution. With the increase of iodine concentration, the rate of reaction also increased.

Effect of pH of the Solution on the Rate.—The reactions were studied at different acid concentrations. It was found that with the increase of pH, the rate of reaction increased considerably. pH of the solutions varied between the limits 0.92 and 1.74. A linear relationship was found to hold when $\log k$ was plotted against pH (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Influence of Temperature on the Reaction Velocity.—The reaction velocities were studied at four different temperatures. In all the experiments, the initial concentrations of hydroxylamine and iodine were kept the same. The reaction obeyed the Arrhenius equation in the temperature range studied and a plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$ provided a straight line (Fig. 2), from the slope of which the activation energy was calculated as 6.9 ± 0.5 kcal./mole. The value of the activation energy, obtained graphically, was checked by using the method of least squares.

It is well known that iodine in solution exhibits different ionic species, such as I_2^- , I_3^- , HOI, and H_2OI^+ , depending on the concentration of iodine and H^+ , and these are believed to be governed by the following equilibria :

The rate of reaction decreases with the increase of iodide ion and therefore I_3^- cannot act as the reacting entity, since in that case the reaction would have increased with the increase of iodide ions. It may be therefore assumed that either HOI or H_2OI^+ acts as the reacting species. Should H_2OI^+ be the reacting entity, the reaction would have been increased, since any increase in the concentration of hydrogen ion would lead to an increase in

the concentration of H_2OI^+ in the equilibrium mixture. As we observed in the present case, the rate decreases with the increase of H^+ ion and this suggests that HOI is the reacting entity; for, any increase in H^+ -ion concentration leads to a decrease in HOI concentration. The concentration of HOI, however, plays a significant role in some other reactions also. Thus, according to Roebuck⁸, the speed of reaction between iodine and arsenious acid depends on the concentration of HOI formed by the hydrolysis of iodine; also the rate increases with the increase of pH of the solution. This may also be explained in the light of oxidation-reduction potential of iodine-iodide system, which can be altered by varying the iodide and (or) iodine concentration. The potential decreases with increasing iodide content. On the other hand, it is known that oxidation potential in some systems can also be influenced by the hydrogen-ion concentration. Since hydrogen ions are not involved in iodine-iodide systems, the oxidation potential is not appreciably affected by the hydrogen ions. So the dependence of the reaction between hydroxylamine and iodine further justifies that H^+ ions also play a significant role, which is formed by the partial hydrolysis of I_2 solution, and hence HOI is the reacting entity.

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DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGES OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

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